

FPGA Based model of 3-Phase Induction Motor using VHDL

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Abstract—This paper addresses the increasing demand for advanced electric motor testing, driven by the surge in Electric Vehicles (EVs) and the need for sustainable transportation solutions. Conventional testing methods for electric motors are often costly and time-intensive. To overcome these limitations, this research introduces a novel, reprogrammable FPGA-based model of a 3-phase induction motor, focusing on real-time motor testing using the Hardware-in-the-Loop (HIL) technique. The induction motor model is coded in Very High-Level Hardware Descriptive Language (VHDL) using AMD Xilinx Vivado software. This approach improves cost-effectiveness, efficiency, and performance in hardware testing. The methodology involves the development of lookup tables, generated using Python, to represent the motor's three-phase input voltage, stator magnetomotive force (MMF), and rotor characteristics (torque, speed, current). These components are then implemented as synthesizable VHDL entities on an FPGA. Power analysis and simulation results for each module are presented. This work establishes a foundational framework for simulating induction motors on FPGAs, offering a significant step towards more advanced and cost-efficient testing environments, particularly for EV motor design and development

Index Terms—Hardware-in-the-Loop, FPGA-in-the-loop, Induction Motor, VHDL, Python, VS Code, TerosHDL and AMD Xilinx Vivado.

I. INTRODUCTION

The demand for Electric Vehicles (EVs) has surged in recent years due to increasing environmental concerns, technological advancements, and the growing need for sustainable transportation. According to the European Union, the transport sector contributes approximately 28% of total carbon dioxide emissions [1]. In the process, electric vehicles have emerged as a viable solution to mitigate these emissions while addressing the ongoing energy crisis.

Despite being considered an emerging technology today, electric vehicles have a historical legacy dating back to the late 19th century, with early models developed by pioneers such as Thomas Parker and Ferdinand Porsche. During the 1920s, Electric vehicles constituted nearly 28% of the United States automotive market [2]. However, the rapid evolution and affordability of internal combustion engine vehicles led to a significant decline in the adoption of electric vehicles.

In recent decades, the electric vehicle market has experienced a resurgence, driven by progress in battery technology,

increased environmental awareness, and supportive government policies. Contemporary electric vehicles are generally classified as battery electric vehicles (BEVs), hybrid electric vehicles (HEVs), and fuel cell electric vehicles (FCEVs), each comprising key components such as an electric motor, battery, control unit and charger [3]. With the accelerated adoption of electric vehicles, the demand for comprehensive testing of diverse electric motor technologies, each exhibiting distinct characteristics in terms of efficiency, torque output, and scalability has increased significantly.

Conventional testing methods that rely on physical prototypes are costly and time-intensive. To overcome these limitations, the integration of Hardware-in-the-Loop (HIL) simulation and Field-Programmable Gate Array (FPGA)-based modeling presents a robust alternative. HIL facilitates real-time testing of motor control systems without necessitating physical hardware, while FPGAs offer high-speed, reconfigurable emulation of different motor types. This integrated approach significantly reduces R&D expenditure, accelerates development cycles, and provides a scalable framework to optimise electric motor performance in EV applications.

II. ELECTRICAL MACHINES.

Electric Motor is the device that converts electrical energy into mechanical energy by using electromagnetic phenomena. Most electrical machines develop their mechanical torque by interacting with current carrying conductors in a direction at right angles to a magnetic field [4]. The first motor was discovered in 1740, which was Electrostatic device which worked by using Electrostatic force, by a Scottish Monk Andrew Gordon and an American experimenter Benjamin Franklin [5]. Electric drive technologies have rapidly evolved in last few decades. The three main machines are DC motor, Induction and Synchronous machine. With intense research, other variations of electric machines now existed like Brushless motor, Permanent magnet machines etc. With advancements in micro-controllers, different motor control technologies are available depending on the user's need [6].

A. DC Motor.

DC (Direct current) motor has been widely used in many applications, electric vehicles (EV's), robotics, steel rolling

mills, etc. The operation is based on interaction between magnetic field produced by stationary and rotating components. The electrical current flows through the armature winding that creates magnetic field, then interacts with the magnetic field produced by stator. This interaction generate mechanical torque that causes the rotor to rotate. They have a precise speed control. It works on DC power supply. They have a high starting torque, which makes them suitable for the application which required high starting torque. They are high maintenance because of more parts. DC motor provides excellent speed control for acceleration and de-acceleration. There are several controllers like, PI (Proportional Integral), PID (Proportional Integral Derivative), FLC (Fuzzy Logic Controller). The excitation state is responsible to energise the field winding which creates the magnetic field necessary for motor operation. There are three such state, Separately excited, Series excited and shunt excited [7].

B. Permanent Magnet DC Motor.

It is a type of DC motor that requires a permanent magnet to create the magnetic field required for the operation of the DC motor. They are commonly used as a starter motor in automobile, windshield wiper etc. The working principle of the PMDC motor is similar to that of the general DC motor, that is, when a current-carrying conductor enters the magnet field, the conductor experiences the mechanical force and the direction of this force is governed by Fleming's left-hand rule. In PMDC, the armature is placed inside the magnetic field of a permanent magnet, and the armature rotates in the direction of the force generated. Each conductor of the armature experiences a force and the integration of all these forces produces a torque that tends to rotate the armature [8].

C. Brushless DC Motor.

The brushless DC motor (BLDC) is a major advancement in electric motor technology, offering improved efficiency and reliability by eliminating brushes and commutators. It uses electronic commutation, reducing maintenance, and ensuring smoother operation. The rotor's equipped with permanent magnets that interact with the stator's magnetic field to generate rotational motion, making them highly efficient compared to traditional brushed motors. Similarly, Permanent Magnet Synchronous Motor (PMSM) utilise permanent magnets embedded in the rotor, eliminating the need for excitation current. When a three-phase power supply is applied, the stator generates a revolving magnetic field that synchronises with the rotor's magnetic field, enabling precise control of speed and torque. PMSMs are known for their high efficiency, reduced power consumption, and ability to deliver high torque across a wide range of operating speeds. Variable Frequency Drives (VFDs) allow smooth speed control by adjusting the timing and amplitude of the stator's magnetic field, optimising performance for specific applications. BLDC and PMSM motors are critical advancements in electric motor technology, offering superior efficiency and reliability. Their applications

span electric vehicles and industrial automation, driving innovation and sustainability by providing precise control, reduced maintenance, and improved overall performance [9].

D. Induction Motor

The induction motor, also known as the asynchronous motor, is widely used in electric vehicles (EVs) and hybrid electric vehicles (HEVs) due to its reliability, efficiency, and robust design. Invented by Nikola Tesla, it operates on the principle of electromagnetic induction, converting electrical energy into mechanical energy without a direct electrical connection to the rotor. The motor consists of a stator and a rotor. When alternating current (AC) flows through the stator windings, it produces a rotating magnetic field that induces current in the rotor, generating torque. Induction motors are classified as single-phase or three-phase, with three-phase motors—using star or delta connections—commonly employed in industrial, commercial, and EV applications due to their efficiency and smooth operation. Based on rotor design, induction motors are categorized into squirrel cage and wound rotor types. The squirrel cage rotor is most common because of its simplicity, durability, and low maintenance, while wound rotor motors allow better control of speed and torque. The air gap between the stator and rotor affects performance, where smaller gaps improve efficiency but increase friction. Overall, the induction motor's precision, durability, and energy efficiency make it a critical component in EV and HEV systems [10].

III. ELECTRIC MOTOR SELECTION.

As reviewed above, induction motors are among the most widely used electrical machines in industry due to their robustness, reliability, simplicity, and low maintenance requirements. They operate on the principle of electromagnetic induction, where a three-phase AC supply to the stator windings generates a rotating magnetic field (RMF). This RMF induces currents in the rotor, producing torque and causing rotation [11]. Because of their rugged construction and cost-effectiveness, induction motors are commonly used in applications such as pumps, fans, compressors, and machine tools. However, their speed control is limited, and efficiency may decrease at low operating speeds. DC motors, supplied by direct current, are available in brushed and brushless configurations. Brushed DC motors use brushes and a commutator for current reversal, offering high starting torque and simple speed control but requiring regular maintenance. In contrast, brushless DC motors employ electronic commutation, providing higher efficiency, improved reliability, and reduced maintenance at the expense of more complex control systems. These features make DC motors suitable for applications requiring precise speed control, such as robotics and electric vehicles. Synchronous motors operate at a constant speed synchronized with the AC supply frequency, ensuring accurate speed regulation [12]. Types such as synchronous reluctance motors and permanent magnet synchronous motors (PMSMs) offer high efficiency, improved power factor, and excellent speed control. PMSMs, in particular, provide high power

density and efficiency, making them suitable for industrial drives, HVAC systems, and compressors. Despite these advantages, synchronous motors are generally more expensive and may require auxiliary starting methods, limiting their use in some applications. Overall, while induction motors lack the precise speed control of DC and synchronous motors, their durability, simplicity, and cost-effectiveness make them the preferred choice in many industrial applications. The selection of a motor type depends on factors such as efficiency, torque requirements, speed control, cost, and maintenance considerations [13].

IV. HARDWARE VERIFICATION AND INTEGRATION

The evolution of hardware testing has progressed alongside advancements in electrical machine development, shifting from traditional prototype-based methods to simulation-driven approaches. Historically, testing depended on manufacturing physical prototypes, such as induction machines, which involved high costs, material usage, and lengthy development cycles. Design failures or modifications required extensive rework, making the process time-consuming and labour-intensive. Modern hardware testing overcomes these limitations through advanced simulation and virtual testing, allowing engineers to evaluate and refine designs in a virtual environment before physical implementation. This enables rapid iteration, early identification of design issues, and significant reductions in development time and cost. Unlike conventional methods, virtual simulations allow quick design adjustments, enabling engineers to explore multiple configurations and optimise performance efficiently. Furthermore, modern simulation tools enable testing under a wide range of operating conditions, including varying loads and environmental factors. By analysing system behaviour and performance early in the design stage, engineers can enhance efficiency, reliability, and overall product quality. As a result, simulation-based hardware testing streamlines the development process, improves design flexibility, and ensures high-performance, cost-effective, and reliable systems [14].

A. *Hardware-in-the-Loop (HIL)*.

Hardware-in-the-Loop (HIL) simulation is a critical technique used in the development and validation of complex systems across industries such as aerospace, maritime, and electrical engineering. It integrates real hardware components—including controllers, sensors, and actuators—into a computer-based simulated environment that replicates real-world operating conditions. The hardware under test interacts with the simulation through analogue and digital I/O or communication protocols, forming a closed-loop system that enables real-time analysis of system behaviour [15]. The primary advantage of HIL simulation is its ability to reduce the risks associated with testing expensive and safety-critical hardware. By providing a controlled and safe testing environment, HIL allows engineers to evaluate system performance, detect design flaws, and validate functionality before real-world deployment. This approach improves system reliability,

optimises performance, and significantly reduces development time and costs. Consequently, HIL simulation plays a vital role in minimising costly failures and ensuring successful implementation of complex engineering systems [16].

B. *FPGA-in-the-Loop (FIL)*.

Like Hardware-in-the-loop (HIL) testing, Field-Programmable Gate Array-in-the-loop (FPGA-in-the-loop) testing involves integrating Field-Programmable Gate Arrays (FPGAs) into the testing and validation process. FPGAs are semiconductor devices that can be re-programmed after implementation, offering flexibility and versatility in hardware design. In FPGA-in-the-loop testing, a simulation environment is established, comprising mathematical models, software, and other components. The hardware functions, such as controllers and signal processing, are implemented on the FPGA within this simulation environment. This approach is particularly advantageous in applications requiring real-time performance, high-speed data processing, or specialised logic. The FPGA-in-the-loop concept enables engineers to rapidly iterate FPGA designs, validate their functionality, and identify any issues early in the development process. By simulating the behaviour of the FPGA within a controlled environment, engineers can assess its performance under various conditions and refine the design accordingly. By applying simulation environments and FPGA technology, engineers can increase performance, reliability, and streamline the development process [17].

C. *Controller-in-the-Loop (CIL)*.

Control-in-the-loop (CIL) validation is a technique used to assess the functionality and performance of control systems by integrating real controller hardware, such as microcontrollers or PLCs, into a simulated environment. This approach involves setting up a computer-based simulation that emulates the behaviour of the system being controlled. The controller is connected to the simulation, receiving input from the simulated system and sending control signals back to it, mimicking real-world interaction. The primary focus of CIL validation is to evaluate the performance of the controller itself, unlike hardware-in-the-loop (HIL) testing, which emphasises testing sensors, actuators, and electronic components. Through this process, engineers can assess how well the controller responds to various conditions and scenarios, providing valuable insights into its behaviour and effectiveness in controlling the system [18].

V. EXPERIMENT

In the traditional old way, where the entire Induction Machine (selected for this research) is simulated on the simulation software like MATLAB/ Simulink. The controller itself is designed using the simulation software which works on certain calculations that doesn't give the real-time output, and no other parallel processing is possible. This method does not replicate the real hardware where the real Induction machine is implemented, and it is controlled by real controller

which gives the output in oscilloscope or its application. Due to lower efficiency, lower response time, lower accuracy, it was then replaced by the hardware-in-the-loop, FPGA-in-the-loop, etc concepts. The actual machine still simulates on the software. This problem is addressed with the help of FPGA. In this research, the Induction Machine is coded with the help of VHDL (Very High-Speed Integrated Circuit Hardware Descriptive language) and then it is implemented on FPGA board. This machine can be programmed as per the user requirement.

A. Why FPGA?

An FPGA board, also known as an FPGA development or evaluation board, is a hardware platform that integrates an FPGA (Field-Programmable Gate Array) alongside various essential components like I/O ports, memory, and power management systems. The FPGA is the core of the board, a reprogrammable semiconductor device that can be configured to perform a wide range of tasks. The board typically includes various interfaces for external devices such as sensors, actuators, and displays, including GPIO pins, serial interfaces (UART, SPI, I2C), Ethernet, and USB ports. In addition, FPGA boards contain different types of memory, including on-chip memory (block RAM), external memory (DDR SDRAM), and non-volatile memory (Flash). They also include clocking resources like crystal oscillators, clock generators, and phase-locked loops (PLLs) to provide stable clock signals for time-sensitive applications. Power management features, such as voltage regulators and power monitoring, ensure clean and stable power. FPGAs are increasingly used in data centres, with FPGA-based Infrastructure as a Service (IaaS) being a growing trend, offering faster processing and superior power efficiency compared to traditional GPUs. Companies like Amazon and Intel have already adopted FPGAs in their data centres. This flexibility and efficiency make FPGAs an ideal choice for designing induction machines in electronic hardware, where customizability, speed, and power management are critical [19].

B. Why not DSP Board?

The DSP board or Digital signal processing board specifically designed for processing digital signals in real-time. The centre of the DSP board is the DSP chip which is a specialised microprocessor optimised for processing digital signals efficiently. DSP board typically involves using high-level programming languages like C/C++ or specialised development algorithms provided by DSP manufacturer. DSP board has features like FPGA, but the main difference lie in their flexibility and customisation. DSP is implemented using programming language while the FPGA on the other hand when implemented using VHDL or Verilog it will work like a custom build processor, makes it much faster and efficient than DSP board. With all the pros and cons, FPGA board is selected. DSP boards are more suitable for acoustical, audio engineering where the work is directly linked with signals [20].

C. VHDL over Verilog

VHDL (Very High-Speed Integrated Circuit Hardware Description Language) is an HDL language used primarily in electronic design automation. VHDL designs are composed of entities, that is the building blocks of digital circuits. Each entity describes a component such as logic gates, register or subsystem. They have input and output ports. Each entity in VHDL is associated with one or more architecture, that describe the behaviour and functionality of the entity. This can be described using concurrent or sequential statement. VHDL supports various data types like integers, float-point types, pre-defined libraries and packages for processing and other common tasks. VHDL allows the designer to describe the behaviour of the digital circuits using techniques such as process statements, signal assignments, conditional statements, and loops. It supports structural modelling, which allows engineers to specify the hierarchical structure of a circuit by instantiating and connecting lower-level components. VHDL designs can also be synthesised into hardware configuration for implementation on FPGA (Field Programmable Gate Array) or ASIC (Application-Specific Integrated Circuit). Verilog syntax is more like C-language, it is often bottom-up approach where the engineers first start by specifying behaviour of individual component. Both the language different syntax, design philosophies and communities users. In this research, we had selected VHDL language [21].

D. Three Phase Input Voltage

Fig. 1. Basic Block of Induction Motor.

The three-phase input voltage is a sinusoidal voltage signal. The reference voltage is taken as 230 voltage. VHDL code works with binary data but can be feed with integer data to get the maximum amplitude. The logic is built by using the look up table. The look up table works on the logic that a sine wave is generated between 0 to 2π . The logic is built to generate a sinewave. If the voltage is taken as 230, then the maximum amplitude of the look up table will be 230, the number of bits in the sine wave will decide how visual the sine wave would be. It is generally taken as 256 bits to generate a full sine wave without any distortion. The look up table is generated using the Python language by using the NumPy library.

E. Stator

The stator parameters are calculated manually using the motor characteristics:

Fig. 2. Input (V) Sinewave.

Fig. 3. RTL diagram of input voltage

$$V_L = \sqrt{3} \times 230 = 398.4 \text{ V}$$

Number of poles = 4 \Rightarrow Number of pole pairs = 2

$$f = 50 \text{ Hz}, \quad I_L = 2.33 \text{ A}$$

Nominal Torque = 3.69 Nm

$$N_s = 3000 \text{ rpm}, \quad pf = 0.85$$

$$Z_s = 0.001201 \Omega, \quad L_s = 0.01241 \text{ H}$$

$$N = 500 \text{ turns}$$

Assuming all mechanical parts and friction losses are negligible, the magnetomotive force (MMF) is calculated as:

$$\text{MMF} = NI = 500 \times 2.33 = 1165 \text{ A turns}$$

Assuming Y Connection The stator will be coded by using these calculations, the logic is build using python which will give a phase shift of 120 degree and -120 degree. The lookup table will then be created with a phase shift, the lookup table is stored inside the memory, which is called by giving a clock pulse. The logic is built then run the simulation by giving the clock and change the option on waveform from digital to analogue to see the sine wave.

The stator will give the MMF, which will be the input to the rotor. The stator will have a three- phase shift output which will create the rotating magnetic field. The result of the MMF

Fig. 4. Power analysis of input voltage.

Fig. 5. Y and Delta connection.

is then coded again using python language with a phase shift of 120 degrees.

Fig. 6. Stator SineWave output.

Fig. 7. RTL diagram of Stator.

Fig. 8. Power analysis of Stator.

The output can be seen as three phase, each having a phase shift of 120 degrees sine wave, which is the MMF.

F. Rotor

Assuming all mechanical components and friction losses are equal to zero:

$$P_{in} = \sqrt{3} \times 230 \times 2.33 = 928.2 \text{ W}$$

$$P_{mech} = P_{fr} + P_{em} = 928.2 \text{ W} \quad (\text{since } P_{fr} = 0)$$

Mechanical torque is given by:

$$T_{em} = \frac{P_{mech}}{\omega_r} = \frac{60 \cdot P_{em}}{2\pi N_r}$$

$$= \frac{60 \times 928.2}{2\pi \times 1475} = 6.009 \text{ Nm}$$

Rotor current:

$$I_r = 191.507 \text{ mA}$$

Fig. 9. Rotor current, Rotor speed, Rotor torque output.

Fig. 10. RTL diagram of Rotor.

Fig. 11. Power analysis of Rotor.

Thus, we calculated rotor current, rotor torque and rotor speed (which was given). The output waveform gives the idea of Motor operating characteristic. The calculations are thus

feed into the logic of look-up table which is created with the help of python. The look-up table is used to produce an output sine wave. The output is generated with the help of simulation option inside vivado, the rtl design which represents the circuit in terms of register and logical operations between them. Power consumption is helpful in designing as the user will keep an eye on the chip power consumption and design as per the requirement.

There are several methods to observe the output. First, using Xilinx Vivado, we ran the simulation and triggered the output waveform using the clock edge. Second, Chipscope, a debugging and virtual oscilloscope software, can be used by connecting the external FPGA board via a JTAG cable to observe the output [22]. Third, after generating the bitstream and programming the device, connect the FPGA board to an oscilloscope using a USB cable, ensuring the use of a PMOD interface for external components such as I/O, VGA, or USB

G. Power Analysis of Input Voltage Module - See Fig.4

The power analysis of the input voltage generation module was performed using the Xilinx Vivado power analysis tool. This module primarily consists of lookup table (LUT)-based sine wave generation and basic control logic. Due to the absence of complex arithmetic operations and reduced switching activity, the input voltage module exhibits low power consumption. The Vivado power report confirms that this block operates efficiently, making it suitable for continuous real-time operation in FPGA-based motor modelling environments.

H. Power Analysis of Stator Module - See Fig.8

The stator module demonstrates increased power consumption compared to the input voltage stage, as it implements three-phase signal generation, phase shifting, and magnetomotive force (MMF) computation. These operations require multiple arithmetic units, memory accesses, and parallel logic execution, which contribute to higher dynamic power dissipation. The Vivado power analysis indicates that the stator module remains within acceptable power limits while accurately generating the rotating magnetic field required for induction motor operation.

I. Power Analysis of Rotor Module - See Fig.11

The rotor module exhibits the highest power consumption among the three functional blocks due to its computational complexity. This module processes rotor current, electromagnetic torque, and rotor speed using lookup tables and control logic. The increased utilisation of arithmetic and sequential logic results in higher switching activity and power dissipation. Nevertheless, the Vivado power analysis confirms that the rotor module operates efficiently within the constraints of the FPGA, supporting real-time Hardware-in-the-Loop (HIL) simulation and motor behaviour emulation.

J. Power Consumption Analysis

Power consumption analysis was carried out using the Xilinx Vivado power analysis tool for the FPGA-based induction

motor model. The analysis considers the three main functional modules: the input voltage generation module, the stator module, and the rotor module, as reported in the corresponding Vivado power analysis figures.

TABLE I
POWER CONSUMPTION OF FPGA MODULES

Module	Total On-Chip Power (W)
Input Voltage Generation	0.043
Stator Module	0.109
Rotor Module	0.164

The input voltage generation module exhibits low power consumption, as it primarily consists of lookup-table-based sine wave generation with minimal arithmetic operations. The stator module consumes higher power due to three-phase signal generation, phase shifting, and magnetomotive force (MMF) computation, which increase switching activity and resource utilisation. The rotor module demonstrates the highest power consumption, as it performs rotor current, torque, and speed computations using more complex arithmetic and control logic.

Overall, the reported power consumption confirms that the FPGA-based induction motor model operates efficiently within acceptable limits, validating its suitability for real-time Hardware-in-the-Loop (HIL) and electric vehicle motor testing applications.

VI. CONCLUSION

This work presents an FPGA-based real-time simulation framework for a three-phase induction motor using Hardware-in-the-Loop principles. The proposed VHDL implementation enables accurate, reconfigurable, and cost-effective motor emulation without reliance on physical prototypes, making it suitable for electric vehicle drive system development. Future enhancements will focus on integrating real-time three-phase analogue inputs through ADCs, implementing on-chip digital signal processing and control strategies, and incorporating machine learning techniques for early fault detection. These extensions are expected to further improve system accuracy, reliability, and development efficiency.

Contribution: This study demonstrates a scalable FPGA-based induction motor model that enables real-time HIL testing for efficient and low-cost validation of electric vehicle motor systems.

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